

Homicidal tea

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Abstract : Simultaneous deaths of mother and daughter due to consumption of tea served by the hosts were reported to police. Initially death was thought to be due to accidental heart attack but the simultaneous deaths were a pointer towards unnatural deaths. Seized articles related to the preparation of tea, blood and viscera of the victims (after postmortem) were investigated thoroughly using routine analysis, HPTLC and GC-MS experiments. The results confirmed the presence of carbofuran in the tea served and deaths were cold blooded murders by pesticides poisoning.

Keywords : Blood, carbofuran, GC-MS, homicide, pesticides, tea, viscera.

Introduction

Central Forensic Science Laboratory (CFSL), Kolkata is a premier forensic institute in India and located at Kolkata for the forensic investigation, research and analysis of forensic exhibits. Examination of cases consists of regular routine examination of forensic exhibits of varied nature (e.g. scheduled or addictive drugs, explosives and detonators, toxicological substances) depending on the queries from the judiciary and law enforcing authorities. However, according to protocols of forensic examination, results of routine investigation must be validated and authenticated with sophisticated instruments having high precision and accuracy¹. This is particularly very relevant for toxicological analysis. The guidelines are imperative for identifying the culprits and proper judgment to ensure that no innocent suffers but actual culprits are punished. Many of the cases encountered in Toxicological laboratory are intricate and require careful investigation². Uniqueness of some of the cases demands thorough investigations following proper forensic protocols.

The case presented here is related to one from Tripura where taking cups of innocent drinks like tea caused the death of two ladies (mother and daughter). The deaths were supposed to be purely accidental due to heart attack as there were no traces of injuries or other indications of murder. But the simultaneous deaths of mother and daughter aroused suspicion and the deaths appeared to be abnormal to the relatives. They suspected it to be a sinister design for cold blooded murder with no positive evidence. The case was reported to the local police.

The police seized tea kettles, cups, tea leaves, sugar and milk powder (all materials related to the preparation and serving the tea) from the house where tea was served. The police also collected sugar, tea leaves and milk powder of the shop from where they were purchased. The collected materials were sent to CFSL, Kolkata for investigative analysis.

The bodies of the victims were sent for postmortem examination and the viscera and blood of the victims were also sent to CFSL, Kolkata for forensic investigation for supportive post mortem data regarding the cause of death-accident or cold blooded murder.

The results of the investigation are presented in this article.

Materials and methods :

Materials : Kettles, cups, tea leaves, sugar, milk powder, materials related to the preparation and serving tea (from the house and shop described before), blood and viscera of the victims formed the experimental materials in the present case. *N*-Hexane, acetone, chloroform, ammonia, silver nitrate and other chemical utilized were AnalaR variety from E. Merck, reference standards of caffeine, drugs, pesticides like carbofuran, baygon, carbaryl etc., were from Supelco, USA.

Methods : Since the present case was related to death, the concentrated efforts were made to find the possible existence of pesticides, drugs or other poisonous substances in the tea served and consumed by the deceased persons. All the samples including contents of kettles, tea

cups, milk and tea leaves were washed and treated with *n*-hexane, acetone and chloroform individually to extract the pesticides, drugs or other poisonous substances³. The individual extracts were subjected to TLC experiments with *n*-hexane : acetone (80 : 20) as the eluting solvent. Development of TLC plates for indication of pesticide groups like organochloro, organophosphorus, synthetic pyrethroids etc. gave negative results. But, when the spots on the TLC plates were developed by spraying ammonia-

cal AgNO₃ solution as a developing solvent and the plates were heated at 110 °C in an oven for 10 min, black spots were observed in the extracts of tea served in the kettle, tea leaves and from the cups. Black spots were supposed to be due to carbamate from its appearance⁴. For confirmation the equivalent portion of the black spots were scooped out by running a preparative TLC and the contents were subjected to GC-MS analysis after dissolution in *n*-hexane⁵⁻⁸. A typical TLC plate is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. TLC of tea extract and carbamate pesticides.

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of tea extract giving black spot with ammoniacal AgNO₃.

Analysis of viscera : 50 g of viscera was mixed with 50 g anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and macerated into fine slurry. 50 mL *n*-hexane was added and heated for an hour in a boiling water bath. The contents were cooled and filtered. The residue was extracted twice with 25 mL of *n*-hexane. The *n*-hexane extract were combined and extracted with 15 mL, 10 mL and 10 mL portions of acetonitrile in a separating funnel. The acetonitrile layers were combined and diluted 10 times with water. The mixture was treated with 25 mL saturated Na₂SO₄ solution and the contents were extracted thrice with 25 mL portion of

n-hexane. The *n*-hexane extract was then passed through anhydrous Na₂SO₄ to remove water and concentrated to 5 mL by passing dry hot air. The content was subjected to HPTLC analysis.

HPTLC silica gel plates (Merck, Germany), (20 cm × 10 cm × 0.5 mm) were activated by heating the plate in the Camag TLC plate heater at 120 °C for 10 min before experiment. The hexane extracts of viscera, tea and kettle extracts, tea leaves, sugar, milk, different pesticides standards like carbofuran, baygon, carbaryl in hexane (2 μL and 3 μL each) were spotted on the TLC

Fig. 3. Mass spectrum of compound at R_f value 7.85 of Fig. 2.

Fig. 4. Structure of carbamate pesticides and caffeine.

plates by Camag automatic TLC sampler 4. The plates were placed in the Camag TLC chamber and eluted with *n*-hexane : acetone (8 : 2).

For GC-MS analysis, 1 mL viscera extract in *n*-hexane was subjected to clean up operations using SPE (Solid phase extraction) method using SPE Accu Bond ODS (C18) 100 mg, 1 ml cartridge. Solvent used for cleanup operation were methanol for pretreatment, subsequently washed with water and methanol and finally eluted with *n*-hexane + acetone (1 : 1)⁹.

The solution obtained after clean up was evaporated to dryness and again extracted with acetone and subjected to GC-MS analysis using Perkin-Elmer Clarus 600 GC and Clarus 600T MS with Elite-5MS (L - 30 m, I.D. 0.25 mm) column. Other parameters were : Injector tem-

Fig. 5. Comparison of chromatogram of different exhibits with standard carbofuran.

Fig. 6. Mass spectrum of carbofuran.

perature : 270 °C, Split : 50 : 1, Oven temperature : started at 100 °C, held for 1 min, ramped to 200 °C at 10 °C/min, held for 1 min, again ramped to 290 °C at 15 °C/min and finally held for 1 min^{10,11}.

TLC and GC-MS analysis were performed to find out the presence of carbamate pesticide specially carbofuran.

Results and discussion

Preliminary experiments showed the presence of black

spots apparently due to carbamate pesticide extracted from tea kettle, tea cups, tea leaves and viscera. The observation amounted to the fact that carbamate present in the tea leaves may be reasons for death i.e. culprit is apparently innocuous tea leaves. However, the portions of samples giving black spots obtained from the tea leaves extract was scooped and dissolved in *n*-hexane. Caffeine and not carbamate was detected from GC-MS analysis of hexane solution of the tea extracts, the presence of caffeine was

Fig. 7. Chromatogram of baygon.

Fig. 8. Chromatogram of carbaryl.

confirmed by library matching (Figs. 2 and 3). The results proved conclusively that tea was not the murderer or cause of death. Structural similarities of caffeine with carbamate may be responsible for the black spot of the tea extract (Fig. 4).

Hexane extracts of viscera, kettle and cups when subjected to GC-MS analysis gave evidence for the presence of carbofuran (a carbamate pesticide). The presence of carbofuran was confirmed by comparing R_f values and by library matching¹². GC-MS analysis of standard carbofuran in hexane solution also confirmed the observation (Figs. 5–10).

The function of Forensic Toxicologist is to combine analytical chemistry and fundamental toxicology to un-

derstand the medico legal aspects of chemicals. Forensic toxicology helps the postmortem examinations to identify and establish the cause or circumstances leading to death.

In the present case, preliminary investigation showed the presence of carbamate arising mainly from the tea extracts which was indicated from HPTLC analysis. However, GC-MS examination with proper library matching of the hexane extracts from viscera, cups and kettle conclusively showed the presence of carbamate, but no such evidence was obtained from tea leaves extracts. GC-MS analysis of standard carbofuran also confirmed the presence of pesticides in the viscera, tea kettle and tea cups. TLC experiments and GC-MS analysis showed no evidence of pesticides and other drugs except carbofuran.

Fig. 9. Spectrum of baygon.

Fig. 10. Spectrum of carbaryl.

Conclusion

The experimental evidences showed that the death of the victims (mother and daughter) was due to pesticide carbofuran served in the homicidal tea.

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Datta *et al.* : Homicidal tea

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